

Managing Digital Technologies through Physical Education and Sports

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Abstract:

This article examines the concept of professional culture in general and the professional culture of teachers of physical education and sports. The role of professional culture in the field of physical education and sports is analyzed. Possible ways of its formation are considered.

Keywords: professional culture, future physical education teachers, professional individuality.

INTRODUCTION.

The changes taking place in physical education require the use of new methods and approaches in the educational field of training future physical education teachers, namely their professional culture. These requirements apply to specialists in any field of physical education and sports.

Professional culture is an indicator of the social maturity of a physical education specialist; it unites a complex of professional knowledge, abilities, skills, and personal qualities.

The purpose of the article is to determine the theoretical foundations for the formation of the culture of a future specialist in the process of his professional training at a university.

Higher school in the field of sports and health needs to prepare specialists for a variety of creative activities: professional, socio-political and sociocultural, provide not only knowledge of a certain range and volume, but also lay the foundation for social initiative, the ability to work with and for students.

The fact that future physical education teachers perceive education as a pragmatic value allows us to consider the content of education and upbringing as the main directions for the formation of the professional culture of future specialists.

Based on a systemic principle, which provides for a comprehensive analysis of the formation of the culture of a future physical education teacher, two main directions are distinguished: intellectually developmental and professionally formative.

The educational system is designed to prepare future physical education teachers who are able to learn easily, quickly adapt to changing conditions and the content of professional activity, who know how to find contact with their students and their parents, who are interested in their continuous self-education and self-improvement in order to achieve high results for their students. And also, education and upbringing are designed to form in the future specialist such personal qualities and abilities that will allow him to independently navigate the professional world and determine the vector of his professional growth, the general style of professional life.

Vocational pedagogical education is a system of training pedagogical personnel (physical education teachers, coaches) for secondary schools and other educational institutions in pedagogical universities and institutes, pedagogical colleges, universities, sports schools and clubs; in a broad sense, training of teaching and scientific-pedagogical personnel for educational institutions of all types. Such education is aimed at training physical education teachers with a high level of professional competence based on the latest achievements of science, modern specialized knowledge of a particular field; with a high level of pedagogical competence, critical thinking, and the ability to apply scientific knowledge in practice. Among the priority areas of state policy in the context of the integration of public education into the European and world educational spaces, the problems of constantly improving the quality of education, modernizing its content and forms of organizing the educational process are identified; development and implementation of educational innovations and information technologies.

However, in the professional training of future physical education teachers, there is a gap between the content of the education received and the acquired culture, since students are taught knowledge rather than value orientation, as the most important function of modern education in the field of sports.

The formation of professional culture in the conditions of educational work with future coaches and physical education teachers is carried out in the following areas: development of professional individuality, that is, mastery of a complex of professional knowledge, skills and abilities, and education - involvement in the sociocultural experience of the profession and society as a whole, development a set of qualities necessary for the development of professional self-awareness and creative activity in the field of sports and human health.

Effective ways to form the professional culture of future specialists in the field of sports in a higher educational institution are: the organization of a holistic educational process with nutritional and training process and its orientation towards the development of all components of professional culture (information, design, artistic, etc.); structuring the content of professional training based on an inextricable connection with the mastery of socially humanitarian and professionally oriented subjects, developing professional qualities based on a combination of technical, informative and communicative competencies.

The professional culture of a future physical education teacher should be formed through targeted pedagogical influences on the personality of the future coach-teacher through the disclosure of the student's capabilities, motives, and professionally significant qualities in the process of targeted interaction at the "coach-pupil" level.

The pedagogical technology for the formation of the professional culture of future teachers of physical education and sports involves the use of such important components: organizationally targeted, motivational and value-based, and professionally cultural.

We consider the professional culture of a future physical education teacher not only as the sum of professional knowledge, skills and abilities, but also as part of the general spiritual culture, which is manifested in professional competence, management of the educational process, readiness for analysis, evaluation and practical action in identifying professional ethical problems, making independent decisions, providing their students with the necessary knowledge, instilling skills of cultural behavior, communication skills, forming and developing contacts between the student and the physical education teacher, conscious readiness for self-education, self-development, and continuous professional improvement.

We come to the conclusion that the ethics of communication and the high professional culture of the future coach play an important role in this process, which contributes to the establishment of trusting, friendly relationships with students.

- The results of the activities of the educational institution aimed at the development of children's sports should be clearly visible. Including:
- participation in sports competitions held in and outside the educational institution;
- to participate in a specific sports club and perform regular activities, to have theoretical knowledge of physical education and sports;
- mastering the experience of active participation in various competitions;
- acquiring the culture of following the conditions set during competitions, including respecting opponents, being able to listen to the opinions of opponents, and being able to express one's opinion;
- in the process of physical training and sports competitions, participants are curious to learn the rules and requirements of the sport they are engaged in;
- mastering the secrets of organizing their activities during competitions;
- to have the ability to resolutely defend the honor of their communities and their country, to develop a sense of love for the country, to fight for its honor;
- acquire the skill of listening to their opponents with kindness and respect;
- such as following healthy lifestyle rules that are safe for themselves and those around them.

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